

Principles in Elementary School Curriculum Development

Nia Pratiwi Hasan¹, Oktavian Ali², Febrianti Tangahu³, Sri Dianita Ngau⁴, Istianti Bulla^{5*}, Desi Frestyawaty Lukman⁶, Ida Fauziah S. Lakoro⁷, Putri Sandika Yusuf⁸, Moh Arif⁹, Marsella Desriyarini Gui¹⁰

Faculty of Teacher Training and Education / Pohuwato University

Corresponding Author: Istianti Bulla aistibulla129@gmail.com

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Curriculum, Research, Education, Development, Principles

Received : 3 November

Revised : 18 November

Accepted: 20 December

©2023 Hasan, Ali, Tangahu, Ngau, Bulla, Lukman, Lakoro, Yusuf, Arif, Gui: This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

ABSTRACT

This research focus to investigate the key principles of the development curriculum in elementary school (SD). The factors such as relevance, holistic, participatory, and conformity with educational standards are the main focus in designing an effective curriculum. Furthermore, the research also highlights the flexibility, interconnectedness between the subjects, and problem-solving orientation as crucial elements in developing a curriculum that is responsive to student needs. Moreover, active learning approaches, formative and summative assessments, and the use of educational technology are integrated to ensure a comprehensive learning experience. The research objective is to make a contribution to the development of an elementary school curriculum that is more adaptive and supports student's comprehensive development

INTRODUCTION

According to Law No. 2 of 1999, the curriculum is a set of regulatory plans regarding the content and learning materials. As well as the methods used to organize teaching and learning activities. Until now, the definition of curriculum put forward by experts is not the same. But there is one thing that is often mentioned in the curriculum. Namely, the curriculum is related to planning student activities and is usually connected with teaching and learning activities to achieve a number of goals. Meanwhile, in its development the curriculum must be based on strong and sturdy foundations or principles. Because of the curriculum principle, it can be used as a starting point. Because the principles of the curriculum can be driven by certain reforms.

Education is an effort to prepare students to be able to live well in society. And able to develop and improve the quality of his own life. And can contribute meaningfully in developing and improving the quality of society and the nation (Nanang, 2000:1).

The applicable state principles determine the world of education. Education in Indonesia is based on Pancasila because Pancasila is the principle of the state. Therefore, the principles of education are no different from the curriculum currently being used. Thus "curriculum principles" were created, which serve as the basis of all current curricula.

According to Muhaimin (2003: 182), the definition of curriculum in the narrow sense is a set of plans and arrangements regarding learning content and materials as well as methods used as guidelines for organizing teaching and learning activities in schools. This understanding underlines the existence of 4 main components in the curriculum. Namely objectives, content or materials, organization and strategy.

LITERATURE REVIEW

To develop a curriculum, a strong foundation is required. If the development process is carried out randomly without a strong foundation, the resulting educational output will not be of high quality. Philosophy, psychology, socioculture, science and technology are the basis for curriculum development. Law number 20 of 2003 states that the curriculum consists of a set of plans, regulations regarding content, learning materials and appropriate methods as a guide in implementing the teaching and learning process. In the curriculum there is a set of learning plans, material content, materials and the learning process. These are the most important parts of the learning objectives. The curriculum also regulates evaluation models in determining benchmarks for students' learning success. In realizing this curriculum, it is necessary to study further how to determine the right curriculum to be used in educational units so that development in the curriculum is needed.

Curriculum principles function as a basis for creating, compiling and developing curriculum. During its development, the principle allows the curriculum to develop in accordance with the required educational standards.

METHODOLOGY

In this article, we use data collection methods. Data collection methods are the methods used to collect and analyze data. By collecting data, researchers can answer certain questions, test hypotheses, and assess results. This method can be chosen according to needs. Researchers can also carry out several data collection methods at once.

Data collection steps will start from determining the information you want to collect, determining the time period, determining the data collection method, carrying out data collection, and ending with data analysis.

This article also uses the Documentation method, a method used to obtain data and information in book form. In this case, the analyzer will collect documents related to the discussion will be discussed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Discussion of Curriculum Principles

1. Philosophical Principles

Philosophical principles are the conceptual foundation that forms the country's education system. They help people understand what Education, principles, and knowledge mean. This philosophical understanding contributes to the formation and implementation of the curriculum in Indonesia. (Hakpantria, Shilfani 2021, 16). Schools try to educate children to be "good" people. "Good" factors are not only based on national philosophy, values or traditions, but also by educators, parents, communities and even the world. The curriculum is closely related to state philosophy, especially in terms of determining educational goals that must be achieved through formal education. The curriculum must be able to ensure the achievement of national education goals to improve people's lives and form valuable character and civilization. Therefore, the philosophical principles related to educational goals are in line with state philosophy. Different philosophical theories in each country have an impact on educational goals, learning materials, learning methods and evaluation methods.

2. Psychological Principles

The principles of psychology are divided into 2, namely: child psychology and learning psychology

a. Child Psychology

Schools are created to help children and help them develop. For centuries, children were considered equal to adults. This seems to be caused by a curriculum that prioritizes materials, while children are "forced" to adapt to these materials in any difficult circumstances. Although children have different needs according to their development. In the early 20th century, greater attention to children became one of the pillars of curriculum development. Then came the progressive school, a curriculum that focused entirely on children's interests and development. This curriculum can be seen as a reaction to the curriculum required by adults without considering the needs of children. Several things that need to be considered in curriculum development are:

- Children are not miniature adults
- The function of school includes developing the child's personality as a whole.

- Child factors must really be considered in curriculum development
- Children must be the center of education/subjects of learning and not objects of learning.
- Each child is unique, has its own characteristics, different from the others. The curriculum should take into account the child's uniqueness so that he or she develops as far as possible according to his or her talents.
- Although each child is different from the others, there are also many similarities between them. So part of the curriculum can be the same for all.

b. Learning Psychology

Education in schools is provided with trust and confidence that children can be educated, their behavior can be influenced. Children can learn, can master a certain amount of knowledge, change their attitudes, accept norms, master a number of skills. The important question is: how does the child learn? If we really know how the learning process takes place, under what circumstances learning produces the best results, then the curriculum can be planned and implemented in the most effective way.

Because learning turns out to be a complicated and complex process, various learning theories have emerged which show incompatibility with each other. In general, every theory contains truth. However, it does not provide an overview of the entire learning process. So, it covers all learning styles from the simple to the most complex. Thus, learning theory is used as a basis for consideration in curriculum development.

3. Principles Of Sociology

The sociological basis for curriculum development is assumptions originating from sociology which are used as a starting point in curriculum development. Education is a sociological process through human interaction towards a cultured human being. It is in this context that students are exposed to human culture, are nurtured and developed in accordance with their cultural values, and their abilities to become human beings are nurtured.

Social refers to relationships between individuals, between communities, and individuals and society. This social aspect has existed since humans were born. Because of this, the social aspect is inherent in the individual and needs to be developed in the life journey of students in order to become mature. Apart from the task of education to develop social aspects, this aspect itself plays a very important role in helping students in their efforts to develop themselves. So this social aspect needs to be considered in the education process.

Education is the socialization of cultural inheritance from generation to generation in an effort to make people behave according to culture in accordance with the values and norms that apply. Through education, the nation's cultural inheritance will be well realized. Therefore, students are exposed to human culture, nurtured and developed in accordance with their cultural values.

Education as a cultural process is an effort to foster and develop human creativity, initiative and feelings towards a broader and higher human civilization, namely a cultured human being. And some cultures are universal and some are specific, meaning that in universal culture there are special elements in it.

Children do not live alone isolated from other humans. He always lives in a society. There, he must fulfill the duties he must carry out with full responsibility, both as a child and as an adult in the future. He receives a lot of services from society and on the contrary he must contribute his services for the progress of society.

Every society has norms and customs that children must know and embody in their own personalities, then express them in their behavior. Every society has a different style of values that it adheres to. Each child will have a different cultural background. These differences must be considered in the curriculum. Apart from that, changes in society due to developments in science and technology are factors that really must be considered in curriculum development. Because society is an important factor in curriculum development, society is made one of the principles.

4. organizational principles

This principle is directly related to curriculum organization. An activity to achieve formal education goals requires a clear pattern of material that will be presented or processed to students. The pattern or form of material that will be presented is what is meant by curriculum organization.

The organization of the selected learning materials must be in harmony with the aims and objectives of the curriculum, which are basically arranged from the simple to the complex, from the concrete to the formless, and from the low level (dominant) domain to the higher domain, both cognitive, effective and psychomotor.

Curriculum organization is a very important factor in the development and development of the curriculum and is closely related to the objectives of the educational program to be achieved, because the form of the curriculum determines the content of the learning material and the way it is presented. The organization of the selected learning materials must be in harmony with the aims and objectives of the curriculum, which are basically arranged from the simple to the complex, from the concrete to the unformed, and from lower level domains to higher level domains, both cognitive, affective and psychomotor. Things that need to be considered in relation to organizational principles are:

- Objectives of the lesson material
- Target learning materials
- Organizing materials

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Curriculum principles are the main principles that form the basis for planning, implementing and evaluating education. In conclusion, curriculum principles form the basis for developing learning plans that are appropriate to student needs, current developments, and the demands of educational progress. Several main principles include relevance, flexibility, continuity, sustainability and responsiveness to the development of students and society. By paying attention to these principles, the curriculum can be directed to be more adaptive and oriented towards relevant goals, and can accommodate development and changes in the educational process.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations, so it is necessary to carry out further research related to the topic of Principles in Elementary School Curriculum Development in order to improve this research and add insight to readers.

REFERENCES

<https://educhannel.id/blog/artikel/azaz-azaz-pengembangan-kurikulum.html>

https://www.academia.edu/3326201/Asas_Kurikulum

S.Nasution, *Pengembangan Kurikulum*, Citra Aditya Bakti: Bandung. 1993, hlm.

Curriculum: Foundations, Principles, and Issues

Elementary Education: A Reference Handbook